

Thermo-mechanical behaviour of microwave-cured carbon nanotubes-based polymer composites

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Mechanism of microwave curing

Figure 1. Interaction of microwave with CNTs and hybrid heating of pellets

Tensile & Fracture toughness tests

- The microwave cured specimen were tested at room and elevated temperature to determine the mechanical properties i.e. Young's modulus, tensile strength and mode-I critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}).

Figure 2. Tensile (left) and fracture toughness (right) tested specimen at room and elevated temperature

Results

- With increase in temperature HDPE/CNT composites has shown more elongation than LDPE/CNT composites. The maximum elongation shown by HDPE/CNT composite is 16% at 80°C whereas LDPE/CNT composites has shown 7% elongation at 100°C.

Figure 3. Stress-strain curve of tensile tested specimen at room and elevated temperature

Results and Conclusions

Figure 4. Effect of temperature on tensile strength (left), Young's modulus (middle) and critical stress intensity factor (right) of LDPE/CNT and HDPE/CNT composites

- Microwave processed thermoplastic composites were tested successfully under the thermo-mechanical environment.
- HDPE/CNT composites has shown more resistance to deformation and elongated more compared to LDPE/CNT composites.
- Young's modulus of HDPE/CNT composites has decreased from 7.86 GPa to 2.47 GPa with increase in temperature from room to 100 °C whereas tensile strength has decreased from 20.3 MPa to 6.51 MPa. In case of LDPE/CNT composites, Young's modulus and tensile strength has decreased from 2.56 GPa to 0.062 GPa and 11 MPa to 1.51 MPa, respectively with increase in temperature from room to 100 °C.

Figure 5. SEM examination of fracture toughness (left) and tensile (right) tested specimen

- K_{IC} of HDPE/CNT and LDPE/CNT composites has decreased from 1.811 MPa m^{1/2} to 0.261 MPa m^{1/2} and 1.447 MPa m^{1/2} to 0.071 MPa m^{1/2}, respectively with increase in temperature from room to 100 °C.
- SEM examinations has revealed the failure of composite by debonding of CNTs and fracture of CNTs at the interface.

References

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